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Development of Nuclear Power Plant Basic Principle Simulators as Tools for Nuclear Engineering Education

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ABSTRACT

Our Institute has been developing PC-based nuclear power plant (NPP) basic principle simulators for over 30 years. The main goal of this development is to provide the nuclear engineering education at the university with tools capable to illustrate the fundamental physical processes going on in the primary and secondary circuit of an NPP. The simulators were integrated into our training courses in the last three decades. The firstly developed primary circuit basic principle simulator, PC² is still the most often and most widespread used one despite the fact that it was written for old DOS operating system and thus nowadays is of restricted applicability. Therefore, the development of a new PC²⁺ simulator started in 2016 based on the training experience accumulated and with support of a national research grant. Its scope of simulation is practically the same as that of the old PC² but it has various model extensions and new features. The graphical user interface (visualization/interaction) program module and the simulation model computing module are two separate programs (executable codes) which may run on a single or on two different computers as well. This feature of PC²⁺ allows for using it via internet and opens new possibilities both in classroom exercises and distant learning.

1. INTRODUCTION AND HISTORY

The development and use of PC-based basic simulators has a long history of over three decades. The International Atomic Energy Agency plays an important role in coordinating the simulator development work of various universities and research institutions and in organizing the exchange of information. Their regularly organized technical meetings indicate that there is still a significant need for the development of PC-based basic simulators today [1], [2].

In the last three decades, five different PC-based simulators have been developed at our Institute:

- PC² – primary circuit basic principle simulator (DOS, 1987-88);
- REMEG – reactor trip analyser (DOS, 1989-96);
- STEGENA – steam generator analyser ('part task simulator') (DOS, 1991-93);
- SSIM – secondary circuit basic principle simulator (MS Windows, 1993-95);
- PC² for Windows – primary circuit basic principle simulator with a more complex calculation model (MS Windows, 1997-99);

With the exception of the program REMEG, all the above simulators are related to the WWER-440 nuclear power plant type. Accordingly, they show the fundamental processes, construction and control principles of a PWR with the aid of a WWER-440 as example. The program REMEG, on the other hand, makes it possible for students to study the phenomenon of reactor trip, using the example of the small power Training Reactor of our university.

2. SHORT DESCRIPTION OF OUR SIMULATORS

2.1. PC² primary circuit basic principle simulator

PC² is an educational tool designed for use in nuclear engineering higher education and nuclear power plant training centers for NPP fundamentals training (FIG.1.). The PC² program runs as an interactive and real-time simulator capable to illustrate the control principles and the fundamental reactor-physical, thermal hydraulic processes going on in the primary circuit of a PWR nuclear power plant. Therefore, the simulation model was designed to demonstrate a wide range of primary circuit operations, control of the plant and response of the system to malfunctions. Capabilities include reactor start-up, power range operations and study of xenon-poisoning in accelerated mode.

In order to improve effectiveness of training, PC² was furnished with important features. Users can modify program constants, freeze and continue simulation, save simulation history and replay it, restart simulation under the same conditions, choose from real-time/fast-time/slow-time simulation option and make snapshots.

The PC² package consists of the software (executable under DOS or in DOSBox under MS Windows) and educational exercises, of which the most important ones are the following:

- 1) Introductory exercise (a survey, how to use, extent of the model)
- 2) The effect of reactor physical parameters (delayed neutron fraction, neutron generation time, etc.) on the operational characteristics of the primary circuit
- 3) The effect of reactivity coefficients (Doppler, moderator temperature) on the operational characteristics of the primary circuit
- 4) Study of self-control capability and power control system

generation on the secondary side, feed-water input, steam extraction, measurement and control of the secondary water level.

At the calculation of heat transfer from the primary to the secondary side, heat transfer equations are solved in one-dimension (along the primary coolant tubes), thus the program illustrates not only the time dependence but partly the spatial dependence of the processes, too. This feature is of special importance in making the model more realistic.

FIG. 2. A schema of STEGENA simulator.

The simulation program allows the user to set the values of some construction parameters of the steam generator, e.g. the inner and outer diameter, the heat transfer coefficient and the number of the primary coolant tubes are all changeable. It is also possible to take into account the fouling, the leakage from primary to secondary side and the leakage originated radioactivity in the secondary circuit.

2.4. SSIM basic principle simulator

SSIM illustrates non-stationary thermodynamic and thermal hydraulic processes of the secondary circuit of a WWER-440 nuclear power plant (FIG.3.). Since the secondary circuit operates with two, practically independent, saturated steam turbines, SSIM models only one of them with the corresponding feed-water system and three steam generators in order to save computing power.

The simulator program allows to study stationary and non-stationary processes as well. During simulation the user can interact with the simulated processes, changing the values of various parameters (e.g. reactor thermal power, turbine load, temperature and flow rate of the condenser circulating water, etc.) or initiating failure of different components (e.g. condensate-pumps, feed-water pumps, high pressure feed-water pre-heaters, re-heaters, moisture separators, etc.). The model is extended to simulate the control systems of the water level in the condenser sump, feed-water tank, steam generators and control of the turbine for-pressure.

Detailed schemes illustrate the structure and important process parameters of the main

components. The thermodynamic characteristics of the fluids in the main components are visualized by auxiliary diagrams.

FIG. 3. A schema of SSIM simulator.

In order to make effective use of the SSIM simulator program, the SSIM package includes a detailed model description and a training program consisting of 10 different student exercises.

2.5. PC² for Windows basic principle simulator

'PC² for Windows' is an improved version of the original PC² primary circuit basic principle simulator with a more complex model (FIG.4.).

FIG. 4. A screen using 'PC² for Windows' simulator.

Most important features of the renewed simulator are the following:

- six primary loops are modelled separately (accounting for the interactions), with the main circulating pumps and steam generators;
- the loops are modelled by dividing the primary circuit to 84 control volumes;
- more realistic modelling of the main circulating pumps;
- thermal hydraulics modelling of the primary coolant and of the steam-generators can account for the reverse flow in case of pump failure;
- natural circulation is modelled correctly in case of drop of all pumps;
- pressurizer phenomena are modelled using non-equilibrium thermal hydraulics.

Separate windows illustrate the structure and process parameters of the main components. There are also several diagrams showing the thermodynamic characteristics of the main components to help the understanding of ongoing phenomena.

3. INTEGRATION OF SIMULATORS INTO EDUCATION

The mentioned simulation programs have been integrated into the training courses of our Institute. Normally the programs are used in a computer lab course of some nuclear topic. Most of the students encounter the simulators three to four times during their studies, each occasion being approximately four hours long. For many years, a course named 'NPP simulation exercises' was organized, every occasion of which was dedicated to computer simulations. Nevertheless, during this course not only our self-developed simulators but other computer programs, such as ANSYS CFX and APROS were also presented. At the beginning of the 2000s, a course named 'Simulation methods' was held four times. In frame of this course, students had the chance to learn from the experiences obtained during the development of the simulators.

In accordance with the above facts, a large amount of experience on both the development and application of simulators have accumulated at NTI in the last two decades. One may consider strange that even today the most often and most widespread used simulator is the one developed first, i.e. the PC² primary circuit simulator. Most probably this fact has been caused by two circumstances. On the one hand, the calculation model of this simulator is practically analogue to the volume of knowledge presented during the lectures on reactor physics (theory) and thermal hydraulics. On the other hand, the user interface is simple enough so that students can learn it very quickly and thus they may gain interesting simulation experience and new knowledge even during a single 4-hour-long exercise. With more complex tools, such as the simulator 'PC² for Windows', getting to know the controls properly may take several hours. Therefore, such tools can only be used for longer courses (which span several occasions). Another intelligent trait of this simulator is that the graphics screen representing the time behaviour of physics quantities is very easy to understand due to the well thought-out ergonomic design.

4. RENEWAL OF BASIC PRINCIPLE SIMULATOR PC²

The basic principle simulator PC², which is used most often at our Institute, was developed in DOS operating environment and in Fortran source code in the second half of 1980s. The renewal was absolutely necessary since today it is practically impossible to run such programs on modern, mostly 64-bit architectures without functional errors.

A plan for the renewal was developed about a decade ago. Nevertheless, the actual work was only started at the end of 2015 in frame of the National Nuclear Research Programme supported by the National Fund for Innovation and Development. The renewal is practically equivalent to fully replanning and recoding the program.

4.1. State of new PC²⁺ development

The simulators model and graphical user interface are two separate programs (executable codes), which may run on a single or on two different computers. Their basic development has just been finished and tested, but we plan to continue it with further features. The current state is illustrated on FIG. 5-8.

FIG. 5. Primary circuit schema in the new PC²⁺ simulator.

FIG. 6. Reactor schema in the renewed PC²⁺ simulator.

FIG. 7. Pressurizer schema in the new PC²⁺ simulator.

FIG. 8. Timegraph screen in the new PC²⁺ simulator.

There are five main schemes on the upper left side, one of which illustrates the whole primary circuit (FIG. 5.), the next two show the more detailed structure of the reactor vessel (FIG. 6.) and the pressurizer (FIG. 7.) with their most important parameters, while the last two contains time diagrams of seven parameters selected from more than 300 calculated (modelled) quantities (FIG. 8.) and all the scram signals. On the right side of the schemes, users can keep track of the chosen quantities or the simulator logbook. Finally, there is a control panel at the bottom of the screen with the model time, scram signal and state indicators, and the control buttons. Action buttons are placed not only on the control panel but on the primary circuit schema as well.

4.2. New capabilities of PC²⁺ for education

The new simulator has many useful features for education, most of which have already been implemented, while the others are under development.

One of the most important virtue is that the graphical user interface program module and the computing module are two separate programs (executable codes), which may run on a single or on two different computers as well (in the second case, TCP/IP network connection must exist between the computers). There is fast, message-based communication between the two program blocks. This feature of PC²⁺ opens new possibilities both in classroom exercises and distant learning.

In conventional cases (both program modules run on a single computer), students can run their own simulation and control the system independently. However, the ability to run the modules on different computers allows several new ways of use. Three examples are the following:

- The calculation model runs on the instructor's computer, while each student can connect to it with their user interface as a viewer and follow the instructor's explanation.
- The instructor is able to intervene in a simulation on one or more students' computers by causing an unexpected (and occasionally hidden) minor malfunction that the student has to recognize and try to handle.
- A future plan is to make the user interface module downloadable for our students through our web page. The calculation model would run on a server computer, while each student could connect to it from home with their downloaded user interface and run their own simulation. It would give them the opportunity to practice as much as they want.

Simulations run originally in real time, but they can be accelerated or slowed down, which is quite advantages during the analysis of a short or long transient. It is possible to make a snapshot of the current state and return to it later. This feature gives students the opportunity to retry to solve a given problem as many times as they need. Instructors can also save the data of a whole transient to a file, and replay it later for the students. A unique feature of our simulator is that this replay could also be stopped at any point and continued as a normal, interactive simulation. It gives instructors the opportunity to run and save a complicated transient in advance and let the students cope with the situation at a given point during the course.

The scope of simulation of new PC²⁺ simulator is practically the same as that of old PC². At the same time, the new simulator has various minor model extensions and new features compared to the old program, most of which are of didactical importance:

- now the simulation can take into account the dependence of vertical power profile on the burnup;
- the neutron flux depression effect caused by the control and safety rods is modelled;
- the remnant heat power is now modelled with a more accurate scheme;
- for modelling reactivity feedbacks two, and for modelling boron worth three (more and more complex) levels can be selected.

4.3. Pedagogical techniques to utilize PC²⁺ for various levels of education

In some cases, parts or functions of the simulator may be too difficult to understand for students at lower levels of education. For such cases, it is considered very important that certain functions of the simulator can be turned on or off, depending on the level of education. In this way, the instructor can adjust the amount of information to convey during the training session to the course participants.

As an example, the temperature dependence of reactivity coefficients may be mentioned. In courses/training sessions short of time, constant coefficients (in lieu of the temperature dependent ones) may be used, depending on the consideration of the instructor. If the timeframe of the simulation lab allows, students may also be given the task to design and perform "measurements" on the simulator to determine the temperature-dependence of the fuel and moderator temperature coefficients. The shapes are linear, so they need to determine a total of four parameters, while these coefficients simultaneously affect the transient.

PC²⁺ is primarily used for education and not for operator training, so it was considered admissible to plan and construct a computational model that allows the user or instructor to set unrealistic values for some specific parameters. It gives them the opportunity to demonstrate important physical phenomena and security principles that would be more difficult or impossible with a full-scope simulator. An example is to set the fuel temperature coefficient to zero ("turn off" the Doppler effect) or the moderator temperature coefficient to positive. Instructors can illustrate with these settings the crucial role that the reactor's inherent self-regulating ability plays in a pressurized water reactor. Students also like the difficult challenge to raise the reactor power from 70% to 100% with the above described, unrealistic reactivity coefficients.

Another speciality of the simulator is the ability to turn off certain levels of the safety systems to study unusual nuclear power plant situations. For example, the possible consequences of a failure of the reactor shutdown system may be illustrated by disabling it. Earlier versions of PC² also had such capabilities, but a better thought-out, more advanced logic was built into the new PC²⁺ to turn the safety systems on and off.

The above described new capabilities of the simulator can only be effectively exploited with sufficient depth and scope of documentation and user manuals. According to the replanning and recoding, the quality and details of the documentation have increased considerably. It is planned that eight diverse manuals for exercises with the new simulator will also be developed.

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